

A DIALECTICAL ANALYSIS OF THE DEVELOPMENT OF MARITIME TRANSPORT

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ANNOTATION In the article, based on the principles of dialectics, everything in the world is in constant change and movement. Nothing and the event can remain unchanged. The fact that this process concerns everything, including communication and transport systems, as well as maritime transport, is analyzed from a dialectical point of view.

Key words: river and sea transport, dialectics, discovery, development, need.

According to the principles of dialectics, everything in the world is in constant change and movement. Nothing and events cannot remain unchanged. This process applies to everything. There is only one difference - it's a matter of time. Days, hours and minutes can be enough for some things and events to change. For example, on May 31, 2020 at 00:22 Tashkent time, the "Falcon 9" rocket launched into space by the US company "SpaceX" reached the earth's orbit in a few minutes. It is a well-known fact in agriculture that a seed sown in the ground germinates in a matter of days, and many such changes occur before our eyes. But there are also changes that will take years, centuries, thousands, and even millions of years to change. If we approach this issue from a dialectical point of view, the possibilities of explaining the issue scientifically will expand¹. The presence of an international sea route in Central Asia in ancient times indicates that shipbuilding was also developed here. After all, sea transport cannot be imagined without ships. Already, strong and

¹ Salimov Baxriddin Lutfullaevich. The philosophical role of dialectical categories in human life. *Oriental Renaissance: Innovative, educational, natural and social sciences*. Volume: 1, Issue 6, 2021. -P.406-410.

durable ships were needed to travel long distances and transport heavy cargo. In turn, intelligence, knowledge and skill were needed to make such ships².

Amudarya and Syrdarya, two central rivers of Central Asia, served as important communication routes in international and domestic trade. Many boats and ships sailed on these rivers. Boats transported merchants, tourists and their goods from one side of the river to the other. Clavijo, a Spanish traveler who traveled to Central Asia in the early 1400s, visited many countries and met their kings. In particular, he was in the reception of Amir Temur, who was considered the unequalled ruler of that world. Claviho wrote down a lot of information about the social and economic situation of the Central Asian region. In particular, in his works, he spoke about river communication routes. Claviho said, "At that time, boats sailed on the Amudarya, transporting people from one coast to another, and it was considered necessary to have a special label or decree that allowed to sail to transport people." Two important conclusions can be drawn from this record of Claviho, who was in Central Asia during the reign of Amir Temur: first, there were boats serving people, especially merchants and tourists, on the Amudarya, and they transferred people from one coast to another on cruises; secondly, it was necessary to have a special label or decree to do this work, that is, a license in modern language.

The process of discovery of the main sea routes between the continents began in the 15th century. The opening of new sea routes had its own necessary and objective reasons. The main reason for this was that, by this time, European trade relations with Asian countries had been greatly reduced. Silk, silk and other types of fabrics, spices such as pepper, ginger, and other necessary products, imported from the East, which are very necessary for Europeans, almost did not arrive. It is known that these products were brought to Europe via the land "Great Silk Road". The main point of this road leading from Asia to Europe was the city of Constantinople. This city was conquered by the Ottoman Turks in 1453 and renamed Istanbul. But the

² Salimov B.L. Expression of Dialectic Categories in the Individual's Social Life // openaccessjournals. eu. International Journal of InnovativeAnalyses and Emerging Technology. Volume: 1, Issue 4, 2021. -P.16-18.

work did not end only with the renaming of the city. Turkey's powerful navy has also blocked sea lanes across the Mediterranean Sea and the Black Sea. So, the ancient trade routes that connected Europe with the East for thousands of years ended. This situation did not go unnoticed. It began to have a negative impact on the social and economic development of European countries³. Especially, this negative effect began to be seen very noticeably in the everyday life of the population. The search for new sea routes connecting Europe with the East became a matter of life and death. Therefore, the governments of most countries in Europe are trying to open a sea route from the East to the West, and they are encouraging the activities of sailors and travelers who want to conduct research in this regard. The most active in this matter were the governments of Portugal and Spain.

The discovery of intercontinental sea routes dramatically changed world trade relations⁴. Some cities and ports in the Mediterranean, which were once trade centers, have lost their importance. New trade centers and ports were formed in their place. Because world trade relations have moved from the Mediterranean Sea to the oceans of the world.

The Portuguese's journey through Africa to India accelerated the movement of other European countries, especially Spain. After that, many previously unknown lands were discovered, new sea routes were laid across the seas and oceans of the world. Development also penetrated the discovered areas. The volume of trade relations of Europe with other continents began to increase. It was an important factor in the development of science and technology and the creation of industry. The opening of sea routes and the development of maritime transport gave many countries the opportunity to establish direct contacts and social relations. Places that

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⁴ Бахриддин Лутфуллаевич Салимов (2022) ЎЗБЕКИСТОН ТАРАҚҚИЁТИДА КОММУНИКАЦИЯ ВА ТРАНСПОРТ ТИЗИМИНИНГ ЎРНИ. Academic research in educational sciences, 3 (TSTU Conference 1), 403-407.

took years to reach on land became accessible in months by sea. The issue of cost is that, as is well known, huge sums of money were spent on the movement of overland trade caravans. Several hundred horses and camels were needed to transport goods. Fodder was always bought for these animals. Dozens of porters were needed to load and unload cargo in the caravan. Porters and other servants in the caravan were paid. A lot of money was required to feed, clothe and rest in caravansary for the people in the caravan, who would take part in arduous journeys lasting months and years. These expenses did not fail to affect the products transported in trade caravans. Costs were relatively lower in trade processes carried out by ships on sea routes. hundreds of horses and camels loaded onto one ship. The number of the ship's crew was also much less than the number of members of the convoy. Then the ships stopped as often as the caravans and did not rest in the caravansary and so on. So sea routes were preferred over land caravan routes⁵.

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⁵ Салимов Б.Л. Ижтимоий муносабатларнинг коммуникация ва транспорт тизими билан детерминистик боғлиқлигининг гносеологик таҳлили. Фалсафа фанлари доктори диссертацияси. Ўзбекистон Миллий университети. Тошкент. 2022, 224 б.